

A nonlinear control approach for hybrid thermal solar plants based on operational conditions

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Abstract

Thermal solar plants are commonly constituted of different subsystems, such as the solar collector field, accumulation tanks, and gas heaters, to enhance plant performance. Nevertheless, from a process control perspective, the changes in the subsystem's configuration can cause interactions and compromise the controller performance. Therefore, this work proposes a hybrid practical nonlinear predictive control for a thermal solar plant facility, aiming to improve the plant operation performance by considering mixed-logical dynamic models and including the process constraints as linear mixed-integer inequalities in a single control layer. The proposed strategy is compared with the conventional practical nonlinear control with an external decision-maker. Both frameworks are simulated under actual process circumstances using real meteorological data and validated hybrid models of the CIESOL facility (Spain). This paper makes relevant contributions in some aspects. From the control framework perspective, a new formulation of the hybrid control algorithm simplifies the control structure, excluding the decision-maker structure from its task. Moreover, the present study considers variations in load demand, a novel and significant contribution. The results demonstrate that the hybrid nonlinear controller performs better than

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the conventional approach, with a reference tracking error index approximately 35% lower in a sunny day scenario.

Keywords: Hybrid control, Model predictive controller, Process control, Solar energy, Thermal solar plant

1. Introduction

Generation, transmission, and energy use are human activities with the most significant negative impact on the environment. In recent decades, the consumption of non-renewable sources of energy has culminated in an unprecedented global environmental problem, in addition to leading modern society to an energy crisis in the coming years due to its exhaustion. This panorama claims urgently for alternative sustainable energy technologies to substitute non-renewable sources and to respond to the imperative for minimizing greenhouse gas emissions [1, 2, 3]. In this context, solar energy stands out as one of the most meaningful and promising choices to face this matter, both for producing electricity and providing thermal power. Although the use of solar thermal energy has grown in recent years, there are still concerns about how to make it economically attractive [4].

The application of thermal solar plants is widely spread in several types of systems, for instance, water thermal desalination process [5, 6], ethanol production [7], electricity [8, 9] and food production [10]. Nevertheless, buildings, industry, and facilities are emerging as prominent consumers in the global energy demand, mainly impelled by the high requirement for cooling and heating systems, lighting, electrical supply, and security apparatus. The employment of thermal solar energy in the building sector, mainly for thermal comfort requirements, is triggered by the sector's significant energy consumption, achieving almost 25% of total CO₂ emission worldwide [11, 12]. Thermal solar energy is an alternative to reduce fossil fuel consumption and greenhouse gases by substituting non-sustainable energy sources in the air-conditioning installations, either for cooling or heating purposes. In fact, the air-conditioning cooling de-

mand is totally in phase with the solar energy potential, representing a suitable choice by overcoming the main frailties of conventional air-conditioning systems [13].

The unpredictable and intermittent nature of solar energy production nourishes the quest to increase energy production efficiency and reduce overall operating costs. In this context, control engineering emerges as a solid and adequate field to optimize the use of thermal solar plants, applying control strategies and optimization algorithms to overcome the several and unpredicted plant disturbances and nonlinearities. The use of advanced control strategies can lead solar plants to operate with reduced costs and increase operational hours [14, 15]. Over the past two decades, several studies have shown that advanced control algorithms can increase the efficiency of energy generation of the solar plant [5, 15, 16, 17]. Since a wide variety of solar collector plants and their associated power system make it difficult for a single control strategy to be suitable for all systems' varieties, advanced control solutions must be comprehensively investigated [18, 19]. In [19] the authors settle that, due to the nonlinear characteristics of solar plants, it is highly recommended to account for nonlinear and higher-order controllers.

Correspondingly, it is crucial to consider the association of auxiliary subsystems, such as storage tanks and gas heaters (applied to store and raise the plant's thermal energy, respectively) in the thermal solar plants' control. Although it contributes to improving the overall plant efficiency, combining these subsystems (solar collectors, storage tanks, and gas heaters) can produce several interactions in the control framework due to its operation modes' changes. From the control point of view, considering the phenomenological aspect of the plant and its different configurations, this combination must reside in the so-called hybrid systems. The dynamic behavior of the plant represents the continuous essence, and the configuration of the plant and its subsystems defines the discrete basis. For several years, authors have been investigating the development of control algorithms with hybrid characteristics. Nonetheless, there are still opportunities to examine and enhance the thermal solar plant's performance

regarding these particular features [4, 20].

Menchinelli et al. [21] define a different variable to represent the energy demand and implement two different control layers. The upper one is the Hybrid
60 Model Predictive Controller (HMPC), which determines the operating mode, and in the lower one, the regulatory controllers track the reference temperature for the defined operating mode. Herrera et al. [22] propose a control approach for managing production and consumption subsystems in a solar absorption cooling system based on Model Predictive Controller (MPC) strategy.
65 The producer optimization framework considers all consumers' demand profiles and finds the best combination that minimizes its cost function. Then, it returns a discrete variable to the consumer systems to define which one should operate. The proposed method reduces the computational cost significantly compared to a centralized approach since, in the last one, the number of op-
70 timizations increases exponentially. Recently, Rathod et al. [23] also propose an HMPC based on Mixed Logical Dynamical (MLD), formulating the control problem to provide the optimal water flow and the plant configuration, including or excluding subsystems. Although the authors have linearized the process models and parametrized the input range, the results have shown that this ap-
75 proach can achieve significant savings in electricity and gas consumption. On the other hand, Normey-Rico et al. [14] proposed a Practical Nonlinear MPC (PNMPC) to deactivate sets of solar collectors in case of the inlet temperature be greater than outlet temperature. The authors still propose manipulating the oil flow rate of the activated fields with no auxiliary system involved. Besides,
80 the authors have contributed by implementing a nonlinear control approach in association with the MLD framework.

The results presented by Gil et al. [5] and Álvarez et al. [24] motivate the contributions of the present work. In the work of Gil et al. [5], the authors have implemented a hybrid NMPC for a solar membrane distillation plant, propos-
85 ing to formulate the control law including operational constraints. The system configuration simulated in the previously mentioned work is composed of the solar collectors, tanks, and a membrane distillation module, in which no de-

mand modifications were introduced in the last one. Moreover, the changes in the operating modes were strictly defined, and the controller must respect the relations between modes jumps. On the other hand, Álvarez et al. [24] include a gas heater in the thermal solar plant facility, controlled by a Nonlinear Extended Prediction Self-Adaptive Control (NEPSAC) strategy based on an MLD framework. It is worth mentioning that the authors have not included demand variations as well, and the operational modes are used as the controller degree of freedom and are not related to the operating modes constraints. The combination of operating modes is chosen to achieve the reference temperature, not considering the process requirements.

Based on the preceding, this work presents a hybrid nonlinear model predictive control strategy applied on a thermal solar plant dedicated to an indoor Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning (HVAC) system. The contributions of this work are built on three main aspects:

- the control framework: The proposed algorithm is an extended version of the PN MPC [25] for hybrid systems. By applying the control formulation presented in this work, the overall nonlinear MLD optimization problem can be simplified to a Mixed-Integer Quadratic Programming (MIQP), reducing computational costs significantly and solving the optimization problems for the inputs increments and the operating modes in a single layer.
- thermal solar plants with load disturbances: The proposed control investigation is conducted to improve the thermal solar plant's performance associated with HVAC systems. The present study considers the variations on the load demand, which is a critical aspect of evaluating control capabilities. The necessity to investigate the potential of hybrid control strategies applied to thermal solar plants with load disturbances is a novel and significant contribution.
- control coordinator simplification: This work proposes a Hybrid PN MPC (HPN MPC) that accounts for the process's operating constraints. This

idea focuses on including the process conditions into the controller prediction horizon, which can avoid sudden variations of the manipulated variables and provide the sequence of future operating modes. Using this
120 formulation, the decision-maker structure, often used to define the process operating modes, can be delivered from this task and thus simplifying the control structure.

It is worth stressing that this work differs from the works of Gil et al. [5] and
125 Álvarez et al. [24]. Gil et al. [5] proposed the HPNMPC for a solar-powered distillation process, wherein the operational mode changes are strictly defined, not allowing any mode jumps. Herein, the control strategy is implemented in a thermal solar plant for HVAC facilities (including a gas heater and the coupled load system), and the plant mode can change freely. On the other hand, differently from this work proposal, Álvarez et al. [24] substituted the systems' forced
130 response by a hybrid composition of all the possible forced plant responses, culminating in a combinatorial problem, which increases the number of possibilities exponentially with the control horizon and the number of operating modes. Besides, the operating conditions are used to achieve the control objectives, and
135 the process constraints are not considered.

Therefore, this work presents a HPNMPC for a thermal solar plant considering the load system demand. The strategy is evaluated in a simulation scenario under three conditions: i) sunny day, ii) cloudy day, and iii) miss-match internal model scenarios. To evaluate the control performance, the HPNMPC is
140 compared to a standard PNMPC with an external decision-maker in charge of defining the plant's operating conditions. That is, the process conditions that define the plant mode's status are either internally decided by the HPNMPC or externally by the decision-maker. The control strategy is implemented in the validated solar plant model of the Solar Energy Research Center (Centro
145 de Investigación de la Energía Solar – CIESOL), located at the University of Almería (Spain).

This paper is divided as follows: Section 2 depicts the process description

and the experimental tests to validate the models used to formulate the hybrid controller. Section 3 describes the HPNMPC formulation, including the mixed-integer inequalities constraints proposed for the controller optimization problem. Section 4 presents the simulated results for the three most common scenarios of a thermal solar facility operation and a comprehensive discussion. Finally, Section 5 summarizes this paper conclusions and comments for future works.

2. System description

A thermal solar plant located at the CIESOL center is used as a case study for this present work. The CIESOL plant uses the thermal solar flat-plate collector field to collect solar irradiance as the alternative power source to generate hot water - which is used as the heat transfer fluid. When the collector field does not achieve the desired load system temperature, a gas heater is turned on to increase the water temperature. On the other hand, accumulation tanks are implemented either to store thermal energy (useful when sufficient solar irradiance is not available) or to smooth the solar collector field temperature variations as an energy buffer. These three subsystems must provide hot water to the load systems, which can be: a) the absorption machine, when the plant is operating in the Summer/Cold mode, or b) the heat exchanger, when the plant is operating in Winter/Hot mode.

The CIESOL facility is illustrated in Fig. 1. In this work, due to the period of tests and collected data, the control strategy is implemented in the CIESOL plant operating in Winter mode, thus, using the heat exchanger as load demand system. However, this choice does not affect the essence of the results since the operating conditions can easily be adapted in accordance with the defined load system, changing the reference temperature or reference range, for instance.

The hybrid models of the plant systems are borrowed and adapted based on the works of Pasamontes et al. [26] and Roca et al. [27]. A recalibration of several parameters of the model has been performed to update the plant's actual conditions, using an optimization algorithm for model calibration pur-

Fig 1. CIESOL thermal solar plant facility

poses. The parameter estimations are performed by Mean Squared Error (MSE) minimization problem so that its new values fit the model to the subsystems' temperature dataset. In this approach, the model parameters are defined as decision variables of an optimization problem, which is expressed to minimize the mean squared error between the temperature model curves and the collected data. The optimization problem is presented as a constrained nonlinear multivariable function, in which the bounds of the recalibrated parameters are established according to their physical properties. Therefore, the optimization solver *fmincon*, available in the Optimization Toolbox in MathWorks MATLAB, is employed. The recalibration procedure is performed using a data set for the optimization computation and another set for model validation. The details of the models and the description of each system are provided as follows and the information about model parameters can be found in Appendix A.

2.1. Solar collector field

The thermal flat-plate solar collector field is the primary energy source of the CIESOL plant. It is composed of 80 solar collectors with a total surface of 160.2 m², with south orientation, and operating range from -20 °C to 120 °C.

The solar collector field model proposed here is a simplified lumped-parameter dynamical model [15]. In this arrangement, the temperature variation is no longer dependent on the lengths of the tubes, assuming that the metal temperature is the mean of the outlet and inlet water temperature. The lumped model is widely used for control purposes [15]. When the heat-fluid thermodynamic properties can be considered constant throughout the tubes, lumped model describes the collector field dynamics reasonably and provides less computational effort than Partial Differential Equations (PDE) based models [28]. Equation (1) depicts the solar collector hybrid model.

$$\rho_f \cdot C_f \cdot A_{sc} \cdot \frac{dT_{sc,o}(t)}{dt} = \beta \cdot I(t) - \frac{H_{sc}}{L_{eq}} \cdot (\bar{T}_{sc}(t) - T_a(t)) - \rho_f \cdot C_f \cdot SCS(t) \cdot u_{eq}(t) \cdot \frac{T_{sc,o}(t) - T_{sc,in}(t - d_{in})}{L_{eq}} \quad (1)$$

in which :

$$L_{eq} = L \cdot n_{sc}, \quad \bar{T}_{sc}(t) = \frac{T_{sc,o}(t) + T_{sc,in}(t)}{2}, \quad u_{eq}(t) = \frac{u_2(t)}{c_s}$$

wherein ρ_f is the water density, C_f is the specific heat capacity of water, A_{sc} is the solar collector pipe cross-section area, $T_{sc,o}$ and $T_{sc,in}$ are the outlet and inlet temperature of the solar collector field respectively, β is the irradiance model parameter, I and T_a are the solar irradiance and ambient temperature respectively, and H_{sc} is the global losses coefficient. Then, L_{eq} is the equivalent absorber tube length considering an equivalent flow u_{eq} , the number of connections in a collector field group n_{cs} , the tubes length L , the number of modules c_s , and the actual volumetric flow of the solar field u_2 . The transport delay d_{in} associated with the input temperature can be estimated as proposed by Normey-Rico et al. [29]. The hybrid nature of the presented model is associated with the discrete variable $SCS(t)$, which defines if the solar collector is included $SCS(t) = 1$ or excluded $SCS(t) = 0$ of the system configuration.

2.2. Accumulation tanks

The fundamental idea of the accumulation tanks is storing thermal energy and damping strong solar collector field temperature variations. The CIESOL accumulation tanks have a total volume of 5 m³ each. As can be noticed in Fig. 1, the tanks can operate in three different ways:

- Load mode: In this mode, the system configuration is designed to store thermal energy. The inlet flow enters the upper section of Tank 2, and the discharge flow comes from the bottom of Tank 1.
- Unload mode: In case the system needs to use the tanks' hot water, the plant configuration changes the direction of the fluid, and now the water enters the bottom section of Tank 1 and comes out from the top of Tank 2.
- Out of Service: This mode is set when tanks are excluded from the system configuration, and now water does not flow through the tanks.

The accumulation tanks are modeled considering the stratified approach, described in Eq. (2) for a unique segment. A detailed explanation can be found in the literature [26].

$$\begin{aligned}
 \rho_f \cdot C_f \cdot V_{t,a,s} \cdot \frac{dT_{t,a,s}(t)}{dt} = & \rho_f \cdot C_f \cdot u_1(t) \cdot TOS(t) \cdot T_{f_{t,a,s}}(t) \\
 & + U_{t,a,s} \cdot SA_{t,a,s}(T_a(t) - T_{t,a,s}(t)) \\
 & + U_{t,a,s-1,s} \cdot A_{t,a,s-1,s}(T_{t,a,s-1}(t) - T_{t,a,s}(t)) \\
 & + U_{t,a,s,s+1} \cdot A_{t,a,s,s+1}(T_{t,a,s+1}(t) - T_{t,a,s}(t))
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

wherein $T_{f_{t,a,s}}(t)$ is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_{f_{t,a,s}}(t) = & (T_{t,a,s-1}(t) - T_{t,a,s}(t)) \cdot mode(t) \\
 & + (T_{t,a,s+1}(t) - T_{t,a,s}(t)) \cdot (1 - mode(t))
 \end{aligned}$$

The notation ath is related to the accumulation tank and sth to the tank segment. Thus, $V_{t,a,s}$ is the volume of the sth -segment of the tank, $T_{t,a,s}$ is the temperature of the ath -tank and sth -segment, u_1 is the pump volumetric flow, $U_{t,a,s}$ is related to the contact area between segments, $SA_{t,a,s}$ is the ath -tank and sth -segment surface area, and $A_{t,a,s}$ is related to the internal contact area between segments. Notice that the hybrid essence is associated with the binary variable $TOS1(t)$ AND $TOS2(t)$, which defines if the tanks are included in the system configuration, and $mode(t)$, to define the load or unload tanks mode. Considering that the variable $T_{f,t,a,s}(t)$ basically defines the direction of the fluid, the binary value of $mode(t)$ will define if the tanks are in Load mode or Unload mode. Moreover, the connection of top and bottom segments of the consecutive tanks and the inlet temperature is defined as follows:

$$T_{t,a-1,n_s}(t) = T_{t,a,0}(t) \quad (3a)$$

$$T_{t,1,0}(t) = T_{t,in}(t) \quad (\text{Unload mode}) \quad (3b)$$

$$T_{t,at,n_s+1}(t) = T_{t,in}(t) \quad (\text{Load mode}) \quad (3c)$$

in which $T_{t,in}$ is the tank's inlet temperature that comes from the fluid mixture of the solar collector field, and n_s and at are the number of segments and the number of accumulation tanks, respectively. That is, the top segment of ath tank is connected to the bottom of the $ath+1$. Also, the inlet temperature enters the bottom segment of the first tank in the unload mode and the upper segment of the last tank in the load mode.

The presented stratified accumulation tanks modeling is crucial to develop the presented HPNMPC approach since the differences between the tank segments are evidenced in practice and directly impact the plant operation. Notice that, based on the defined modes, the upper segment temperature of Tank 2 is usually higher than the bottom segment temperature of Tank 1. These temperature gradients must be appropriately considered to define the plant operating conditions.

2.3. Gas heater

260 The gas heater is an energy complement to the thermal solar plant, and it must enter into operation only if the solar collector fields do not provide enough power to the load system. As depicted in Fig. 1, the water that goes into the demand system always passes through the gas heater. The central action of this subsystem is to turn the gas heater on or off. Moreover, it must be noted that 265 this subsystem is a non-renewable energy source, and its use must be avoided or at least minimized. Equation (4) provides the dynamic model of the system:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \rho_f \cdot C_f \cdot V_g \cdot \frac{dT_g(t)}{dt} = & U_{ga} \cdot A_g \cdot (T_a(t) - T_g(t)) \\
 & + GH(t) \cdot U_{gto} \cdot ((\log_{10}(9 \cdot \sqrt{Reg(t)}) + 1) \cdot T_{g,gas}(t) - T_g(t)) \\
 & + \rho_f \cdot C_f \cdot u_3(t) \cdot (T_{g,in}(t) - T_g(t))
 \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

wherein V_g is the gas heater fluid volume, T_g is the output temperature of the gas heater, U_{ga} is a thermal losses coefficient, A_g is the gas heater water conduct's external surface, U_{gto} is the gas heater heat transfer coefficient, $T_{g,gas}$ 270 is the combustion gasses temperature, u_3 is the gas heater and heat exchanger volumetric flow, and $T_{g,in}$ is the gas heater inlet temperature. The hybrid nature is assumed by applying the binary variable $GH(t)$ which represents the gas heater on/off ($GH(t) = 1/GH(t) = 0$) signal. Notice that the presented gas heater model is an improved version of that presented in [26], herein presenting 275 a logarithmic term that relates the gas heater regulation $Reg(t)$ with the gas combustion temperature $T_{g,gas}(t)$. This function was tested and adjusted to achieve the best validated fit results, as presented in the sequel.

2.4. Heat exchanger

The heat exchanger is the load system herein proposed as the energy demand. 280 As described earlier, this system uses the hot water from the thermal solar plant to heat a second coupled system of the HVAC facility. Thus, the HVAC can use the heated water to control the building inside temperature. The machine

is presented on two sides: (i) the hot side, from where the hot water of the thermal plant enters, and the cold side, from where the water coming from the HVAC facility enters. The energy demand can be changed accordingly with the variations of the inlet temperature from the cold side of the heater exchanger $T_{he,c,in}(t)$ and its water flow $u_c(t)$.

In this context, a more straightforward design based on first principles steady-state model is presented in Eq. (5). The obtained equations and model parameters are detailed in the work of Gil et al. [30].

$$T_{sshe,h,o}(t) = T_{he,h,in}(t) - \eta_{he,1} \cdot (T_{he,h,in}(t) - T_{he,c,in}(t)) \quad (5a)$$

$$T_{sshe,c,o}(t) = T_{he,c,in}(t) + \eta_{he,2} \cdot (T_{he,h,in}(t) - T_{sshe,h,o}(t)) \quad (5b)$$

in which

$$\eta_{he,1} = \frac{1 - e^{\theta_{he}}}{1 - \frac{u_3(t) \cdot C_f}{u_c(t) \cdot C_{fc}} \cdot e^{\theta_{he}}}$$

$$\eta_{he,1} = \frac{u_3(t) \cdot C_f}{u_c(t) \cdot C_{fc}}$$

$$\theta_{he} = \alpha_{he} \cdot A_{he} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{u_3(t) \cdot C_f} - \frac{1}{u_c(t) \cdot C_{fc}} \right)$$

$T_{sshe,h,o}$ and $T_{sshe,c,o}$ are the heat exchanger hot and cold side outlet temperatures respectively, $T_{he,h,in}$ and $T_{he,c,in}$ are the heat exchanger hot and cold side inlet temperatures respectively, C_{fc} is the specific heat capacity of water of the heat exchanger in the cold side, u_c is the gas heater cold side volumetric flow, α_{he} is the heat exchanger heat transfer coefficient, and A_{he} is the heat exchanger area.

In addition, a first-order filter for the outlet temperature both of the cold and hot side ($T_{he,c,o}$ and $T_{he,h,o}$ respectively) is proposed in order to provide a dynamic behavior of the heat exchange model.

$$\frac{dT_{he,h,o}(t)}{dt} = \tau \cdot (T_{sshe,h,o}(t) - T_{he,h,o}(t)) \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{dT_{he,c,o}(t)}{dt} = \tau \cdot (T_{sshe,c,o}(t) - T_{he,c,o}(t)) \quad (7)$$

where τ is the time constant.

2.5. Operation modes

The thermal solar plant can operate in several different system combinations. This work presents the six standard operating modes that are practiced in real scenarios. Notice that the system configuration can be related to the state of the binary model variables $SCS(t)$, $TOS1(t)$, $TOS2(t)$, $mode(t)$ and $GH(t)$. Although the variable $Reg(t) \in \mathbb{R} [0, 1]$ can be assumed as manipulated, in this paper, it is applied as a constant value, being excluded from the controller inputs calculation. This criterion is assumed to allow the manipulation only of the plant's volumetric flows since the correlation between the gas flow and the gas heater outlet temperature is very close and would not allow higher variations in the systems' temperature profile throughout the plant.

To express each plant mode mathematically while making it useful for the control formulation, a binary variable $\delta \in \{0, 1\}$ is employed. Table 1 depicts the plant mode and the binary model variables.

It is worth mentioning that the solar field is the central system investigated in this work since it is presented a control strategy that can improve its use and minimize the use of the gas heater. Moreover, when the tanks are excluded from the system configuration, the variable $mode(t)$ is irrelevant since the entire term is multiplied by zero, (see Eq. (2)).

Furthermore, the position of the valves is arbitrarily excluded from the system modes description for the sake of simplicity. However, the adopted plant mode is intrinsically related to the appropriate manipulation of valves $V2$ and $V3$, which can be automatically defined. Also, valves $V1$ and $V4$ are used to control the water flow $u_2(t)$ and $u_3(t)$, respectively, and operate according to the control signal.

Table 1: CIESOL solar plant operating modes definition. *The notation X represents the logical irrelevance of the variable to the binary mode output, which can be 1 or 0.

Binary mode	Mode	$SCS(t)$	$TOS1(t)$	$TOS2(t)$	$mode(t)$	$GH(t)$
δ_1	1 - Solar field	1	0	0	X	0
δ_2	2 - Solar field + Tanks unload	1	1	1	0	0
δ_3	3 - Solar field + Tanks load	1	1	1	1	1
δ_4	4 - Solar field + Gas heater	1	0	0	X	0
δ_5	5 - Solar field + Tanks unload + Gas heater	1	1	1	0	0
δ_6	6 - Solar field + Tanks load + Gas heater	1	1	1	1	1

2.6. Validation of global system models

The models presented in Equations (1) to (7) are associated in order to reproduce the entire CIESOL facility dynamics. Thus, the presented input and output temperature variables are correlated in each equation, as presented in Fig. 2. Notice that only the temperature relations are established in Fig. 2 for the sake of simplicity. The volumetric flow input variables are depicted in Fig. 1.

Fig 2. Temperature relations between the CIESOL facility subsystems. The red variables are the subsystems output temperature, the blue variables are the subsystems input temperatures and the green variables are the tank model binary variables.

In order to describe the subsystems relations, the input/output temperature scheme is depicted in the sequel: starting from the solar collector field, the output temperature $T_{sc,o}(t)$ combines with the inlet temperature $T_{sc,in}(t)$ at the first intersection point P1. This new temperature $T_{p1}(t)$ can be: (i) the accumulation tanks inlet temperature $T_{t,in}(t)$, if the tanks are operating, or (ii) the gas heater inlet temperature if the tanks are out of service, defined by the two binary variables $TOS1(t)$ and $TOS2(t)$. In the case the tanks are in load mode, then the output temperature of the tanks subsystem is the $T_{t,1,1}(t)$; otherwise, the output temperature is $T_{t,2,3}(t)$. Next, the gas heater inlet temperature is, once again, defined by the $TOS1(t)$ and $TOS2(t)$ variables, selecting between

345 the tanks' outlet temperature or $T_{p1}(t)$. The gas heater outlet temperature is
 always the inlet temperature of the load system, in which in this work is the heat
 exchanger, $T_{he,h,in}(t)$. Notice that this is the chosen variable to be controlled
 by the HPNMPC strategy. Then, the system recirculates the water coming out
 from the heat exchanger, mixing it with the gas heater inlet water $T_{g,in}(t)$ with
 350 $T_{he,h,o}(t)$ at the second intersection point P2. This new temperature $T_{p2}(t)$ is
 the solar collector field inlet temperature $T_{sc,in}(t)$. The combined temperature
 at points P1 and P2 are modeled employing static energy balances.

Intending to verify the system modeling equations, Figs. 3 and 4 show the
 validation experiment using real data collected in the CIESOL facility on Jan-
 355 uary 15, 2021. The validation experiment is provided in this work only as an
 example since the model equations have already been proved and validated in
 the works of Pasamontes et al. [26] and Gil et al. [30]. The model parameters
 are defined in Appendix A (Table 9), which were identified by an identification
 procedure based on an optimization algorithm to minimize a Mean Square Er-
 360 ror (MSE) between the plant data and the model outputs. In this section, only
 the validation data set is provided graphically by reason of directness. More-
 over, Table 2 presents the coefficient of determination R^2 for each temperature
 curve, which can represent the relation between the proposed models and the
 real plant data. As can be noted, the model description provided in this work
 365 can appropriately reproduce the complete system operation, including the oper-
 ational mode changes, given an R^2 very close to 1, for the validation time of 2.7
 hours. Therefore, according to the validated model, a model-based predictive
 controller can be adequately formulated.

3. Mixed logic PNMPC

370 The control framework presented here is formulated based on the PNMPC
 algorithm [25]. This strategy computes the nonlinear system outputs, along a
 prediction horizon N_p , as an approximated linear function of the future control
 increments $\Delta \mathbf{u}$. Although the predicted outputs vector $\hat{\mathbf{Y}}$ is an approximated

Fig 3. Meteorological conditions and solar collector input temperature for the model validation experiment.

linear function, this control strategy can adopt nonlinear system models for
 375 the free-response \mathbf{F} , that is obtained if no control movements are performed in
 the control horizon, and the gradient of the prediction outputs relative to the
 vector of control increments $\frac{\partial \hat{\mathbf{Y}}}{\partial \Delta \mathbf{u}}$ for the forced response \mathbf{G} . Moreover, this
 approach can also deal with disturbance models and modeling errors by using a
 discrete filter for the predicted outputs, similar to those presented in well-known
 380 predictive controllers, as Dynamic Matrix Controller (DMC) and Generalized
 Predictive Controller (GPC). Therefore, the control algorithm can be expressed
 by using classical cost function minimization.

Furthermore, the PNMPC control optimization problem must consider the
 operational plant modes as process constraints, producing a MLD problem that
 385 includes binary and continuous variables. Hence, the predictive control is ex-
 tended to a Mixed-Integer Predictive Controller (MIPC) that can provide op-
 timal inputs solution by solving a MIQP problem. This control formulation
 requires the transformation of the logic combinations into linear inequalities.
 Thus, the mixed-logical dynamic system (herein represented as the thermal so-
 390 lar plant) can be described as a linear dynamic equation subjected to linear

(a) Solar collector field and accumulation tanks model validation results

(b) Gas heater and heat exchanger model validation results

(c) CIESOL plant operating modes

Fig 4. CIESOL model validation outputs

Table 2: Coefficient of determination R^2 for the system models validation experiment

Variables	R^2
$T_{sc,o}(t)$	0.98
$T_{t,1,1}(t)$	0.95
$T_{t,2,3}(t)$	0.97
$T_g(t)$	0.96
$T_{he,h,o}(t)$	0.95
$T_{he,c,o}(t)$	0.94

mixed-integer inequalities.

This control section first presents the model output prediction calculations associated with each operating plant mode and it is given the linear mixed-integer inequalities that include the hybrid behavior of the system. Afterwards, the additional standard constraints and the control optimization problem are introduced. Finally, the proposed HPNMPC control strategy is compared to the conventional PNMPC concerning the optimization problem formulation and the process mode determination.

3.1. HPNMPC outputs prediction

The predicted outputs computed by the conventional PNMPC approach can be described as follows:

$$\hat{\mathbf{Y}} = \mathbf{F} + \mathbf{G} \cdot \Delta \mathbf{u} \quad (8)$$

wherein the matrices are defined in the discrete mode for a single input single output case as

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{\mathbf{Y}} &= \begin{bmatrix} \hat{Y}(t|t) \\ \hat{Y}(t+1|t) \\ \vdots \\ \hat{Y}(t+N_p|t) \end{bmatrix}_{[N_p \cdot n_y \times 1]} & \mathbf{F} &= \begin{bmatrix} \hat{F}(t|t) \\ \hat{F}(t+1|t) \\ \vdots \\ \hat{F}(t+N_p|t) \end{bmatrix}_{[N_p \cdot n_y \times 1]}, \\
\Delta \mathbf{u} &= \begin{bmatrix} \Delta u(t|t) \\ \Delta u(t+1|t) \\ \vdots \\ \Delta u(t+N_c-1|t) \end{bmatrix}_{[N_c \cdot n_u \times 1]} \\
\mathbf{G} &= \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \hat{Y}(t+1|t)}{\partial \Delta u(t|t)} & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ \frac{\partial \hat{Y}(t+1|t)}{\partial \Delta u(t|t)} & \frac{\partial \hat{Y}(t+2|t)}{\partial \Delta u(t+1|t)} & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \cdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \frac{\partial \hat{Y}(t+N_p|t)}{\partial \Delta u(t|t)} & \frac{\partial \hat{Y}(t+N_p|t)}{\partial \Delta u(t+1|t)} & \cdots & \frac{\partial \hat{Y}(t+N_p|t)}{\partial \Delta u(t+N_c-1|t)} \end{bmatrix}_{[N_p \cdot n_y \times N_c \cdot n_u]}
\end{aligned}$$

The vector $\hat{\mathbf{Y}}$ is the predicted outputs, \mathbf{F} , is the free response, $\Delta \mathbf{u}$, is the
405 vector of future outputs, N_p and N_c are the prediction and control horizons,
respectively, and n_y and n_u are the number of outputs and inputs, respectively.
Since the forced response is the gradient of $\hat{\mathbf{Y}}$ relative to $\Delta \mathbf{u}$, the forced response
matrix \mathbf{G} , can be obtained in many different ways. A comprehensive explanation
of the PN MPC approach is detailed in the work of Plucenio et al. [25]

410 This paper focuses on developing the Eq. (8) to represent the different plant
modes in a hybrid way. First of all, the notation m_{k-1} is stated, which represents
the plant mode in the instant $k-1$, where m is related with the number of
operating modes, that is $m = 1, \dots, n_m$. Secondly, an auxiliary variable $\Delta \mathbf{z}_m$
is introduced, which relates the system manipulated variables and the operating
415 mode as $\Delta \mathbf{z}_m = \delta_m \cdot \Delta \mathbf{u}$. In this expression, δ_m is the variable in charge of
defining the operating mode, according to Table 1, whereas $\Delta \mathbf{u}$ represents the
system manipulated variables, that is $\Delta \mathbf{u} = [\Delta u_1, \dots, \Delta u_{n_u}]$. Thus, the output
prediction for a hybrid model using the proposed PN MPC formulation is defined

as follows:

$$\hat{\mathbf{Y}} = \mathbf{F}_{m_{k-1}} + \mathbf{G}_M \cdot \Delta \mathbf{z} \quad (9)$$

420 assuming that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{G}_M &= [\mathbf{G}_1, \mathbf{G}_2, \dots, \mathbf{G}_{n_m}]_{[N_p \cdot n_y \times N_c \cdot n_u \cdot n_m]}, \\ \Delta \mathbf{z} &= [\Delta z_1, \Delta z_2, \dots, \Delta z_{n_m}]_{[N_c \cdot n_u \cdot n_m \times 1]}^T \end{aligned}$$

Vector \mathbf{F} is the free-response, calculated over the operating mode in the last instant. The matrix \mathbf{G}_M is composed of each forced response for each different operating mode. Notice that the predicted output $\hat{\mathbf{Y}}$ can be described as a combination of different operating modes¹. In this work, the system output
425 variables are the temperature of the all subsystems presented in Section 2. That is, the future predicted outputs $\hat{\mathbf{Y}}$ and the control inputs are established as:

¹Each matrix of \mathbf{G}_M is calculated by the gradient of the controlled inputs $\Delta \mathbf{u}$ for the specific operating mode m . It means that for each plant mode, there is a respective $\mathbf{F}_{m_{k-1}}$, $\mathbf{G}_1, \mathbf{G}_2, \dots, \mathbf{G}_{n_m}$ and also $\Delta z_1, \Delta z_2, \dots, \Delta z_{n_m}$ associated. The predicted output $\hat{\mathbf{Y}}$ is a combination of the future outputs in the future operating modes, which are determined by inequalities constraints presented in Section 3.2.

$$\hat{\mathbf{Y}} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{T}_{sc,o} \\ \hat{T}_{p1} \\ \hat{T}_{t,1,1} \\ \hat{T}_{t,1,2} \\ \hat{T}_{t,1,3} \\ \hat{T}_{t,2,1} \\ \hat{T}_{t,2,2} \\ \hat{T}_{t,2,3} \\ \hat{T}_g \\ \hat{T}_{he,h,o} \\ \hat{T}_{he,c,o} \\ \hat{T}_{p2} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\Delta \mathbf{u} = \begin{bmatrix} \Delta u_1 \\ \Delta u_2 \\ \Delta u_3 \end{bmatrix}$$

Based on the proposed model description, the control optimization problem must provide the optimal input values and only one available operating mode. The operating modes are defined by process conditions, which are formulated
 430 by employing mixed-integer inequality constraints.

3.2. Linear mixed-integer inequalities

In this work, three sets of mixed-integer inequalities based on the Big-M method are established in order to formulate the control MIQP optimization problem. For the sake of clarity, a generic formulation for the inequality con-
 435 straints is presented in this section, and later the practical thermal solar plant case is given. A deeper study of MIQP formulation and its mathematical programming can be found in [31, 32].

First, to relate each auxiliary variables $\Delta \mathbf{z}_m$ with the corresponding manipulated variables $\Delta \mathbf{u}$ and the binary variable δ_m , the following logic condition is
 440 established:

$$\begin{aligned}
[\delta_m = 0] &\rightarrow [\Delta \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{0}] \\
[\delta_m = 1] &\rightarrow [\Delta \mathbf{u} = \Delta \mathbf{z}_m], \quad \forall m \in [1, \dots, n_m]
\end{aligned}$$

The notation “ \rightarrow ” is the logic statement for “implies”. Notice that the model auxiliary inputs $\Delta \mathbf{z}_m$ will be only equal to the process inputs if the $\delta_m = 1$. This logic statement is traduced into inequalities constraints by the following expressions:

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta \mathbf{z}_m &\leq \Delta \mathbf{u}_{max} \cdot \delta_m \\
\Delta \mathbf{z}_m &\geq \Delta \mathbf{u}_{min} \cdot \delta_m \\
\Delta \mathbf{z}_m &\leq \Delta \mathbf{u} - \Delta \mathbf{u}_{min} \cdot (1 - \delta_m) \\
\Delta \mathbf{z}_m &\geq \Delta \mathbf{u} - \Delta \mathbf{u}_{max} \cdot (1 - \delta_m) \quad \forall m \in [1, \dots, n_m]
\end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

445 in which $\Delta \mathbf{u}_{max}$ and $\Delta \mathbf{u}_{min}$ are the maximum and minimum limits for the inputs.

Next, the system conditions must define the operating process modes. Thus, the definition mentioned above is introduced by the following logic statements and its inequalities expressions equivalence:

$$[f(x) \leq 0] \leftrightarrow [\delta_m = 1] \text{ is true iff } \begin{cases} f(x) \leq f_{max} \cdot (1 - \delta_m) \\ f(x) \geq \varepsilon + (f_{min} - 1) \cdot \delta_m \end{cases} \tag{11}$$

450 wherein $f(x)$ is a defined process condition and ε is a small tolerance in which the constraint is considered violated and “ \leftrightarrow ” is the “if and only if” logic Boolean notation.

455 Lastly, additional logical constraints are presented to consider a combination between different process conditions and their related binary variables. These logical statements are herein presented as Boolean “AND” (\wedge) operator, in the

following example:

$$[\delta_c = \delta_a \wedge \delta_b] \text{ is equivalent to } \begin{cases} -\delta_a + \delta_c \leq 0 \\ -\delta_b + \delta_c \leq 0 \\ \delta_a + \delta_b - \delta_c \leq 1 \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

3.3. Operating constraints

The operating modes are defined as a combination of different process conditions. In this work, the system temperature is defined as the primary variable responsible for defining how the plant should operate. In addition, regardless of
460 the operating modes, the manipulated variables must continue to be adjusted to achieve the control objective when necessary.

First, consider four auxiliary binary variables: δ_{T1} , δ_{T2} , δ_{GH} and δ_{mode} . These variables represent the conditions in which each subsystem can be ac-
465 tivated/deactivated. To operate the tanks in the unload mode, $\delta_{T1} = 1$. On the other hand, to operate the tanks in load mode $\delta_{T2} = 1$. In addition, when both variables $\delta_{T1} = \delta_{T2} = 0$, the tanks are out of the plant configuration. Moreover, to activate the gas heater, $\delta_{GH} = 1$. Finally, δ_{mode} is the auxiliary variable that keeps the system in the operating mode for a certain time. If this
470 variable condition is satisfied, it enables the other auxiliary variables and allows the plant changes the operating mode; otherwise, the plant keeps operating in the previous configuration. Notice that combining these four auxiliary variables embraces all the six previously defined operating modes, as represented in Table 3.

Notice that the notation $\tilde{\delta}$ means the logic Boolean “NOT”. It is worth
475 mentioning that the auxiliary variables are related to the binary model variables defined in Section 2 by the operating modes variables δ_m . In addition, it is established that when both conditions δ_{T1} and δ_{T2} are satisfied, the plant configuration must prioritize to store thermal energy. This strategy is proposed
480 to increase the plant operating time and avoid future uses of the gas heater. Therefore, the modes δ_3 and δ_6 are repeated on the truth table.

Table 3: Truth table for the auxiliary variables and operating modes. *The notation X represents the logical irrelevance of the variable to the binary mode output, which can be 1 or 0. The operator \wedge represent the logical operation “AND” and the notation $\widetilde{\delta}$ the logical operation “NOT”.

Binary mode	δ_{T1}	δ_{T2}	δ_{GH}	δ_{mode}	Output
δ_1	0	0	0	1	$= \widetilde{\delta_{T1}} \wedge \widetilde{\delta_{T2}} \wedge \widetilde{\delta_{GH}} \wedge \delta_{mode}$
δ_2	1	0	0	1	$= \delta_{T1} \wedge \widetilde{\delta_{T2}} \wedge \widetilde{\delta_{GH}} \wedge \delta_{mode}$
δ_3	0	1	0	1	$= \widetilde{\delta_{T1}} \wedge \delta_{T2} \wedge \widetilde{\delta_{GH}} \wedge \delta_{mode}$
δ_3	1	1	0	1	$= \delta_{T1} \wedge \delta_{T2} \wedge \widetilde{\delta_{GH}} \wedge \delta_{mode}$
δ_4	0	0	1	1	$= \widetilde{\delta_{T1}} \wedge \widetilde{\delta_{T2}} \wedge \delta_{GH} \wedge \delta_{mode}$
δ_5	1	0	1	1	$= \delta_{T1} \wedge \widetilde{\delta_{T2}} \wedge \delta_{GH} \wedge \delta_{mode}$
δ_6	0	1	1	1	$= \widetilde{\delta_{T1}} \wedge \delta_{T2} \wedge \delta_{GH} \wedge \delta_{mode}$
δ_6	1	1	1	1	$= \delta_{T1} \wedge \delta_{T2} \wedge \delta_{GH} \wedge \delta_{mode}$
$\delta_{m_{k-1}}$	X	X	X	0	$= \widetilde{\delta_{mode}}$

Regarding the activation of each auxiliary binary variable, the conditions of the system temperature profile are defined with the goal of improving the plant performance, such as: i) maximize the operating time, ii) use the gas heater
485 only when necessary, iii) minimize the outputs chattering effect, iv) minimize significant variations of the manipulated inputs and v) keep small differences between the subsystems temperature gradient. Based on these assumptions, the process conditions are established:

- 1 If the temperature of the upper segment of Tank 2 is greater than the
490 temperature of the water coming from the solar collector field, then unload the tanks.
- 2 If the temperature of the solar collector field is greater than the temperature of the lower segment of Tank 1, then load the tank.
- 3 If the gas heater inlet temperature is lower than the reference temperature
495 limits, then activate the gas heater.

- 4 If the gas heater outlet temperature is higher than the reference temperature limits, then deactivate the gas heater.
- 5 If the elapsed time in the current operating mode is lower than the predefined time, then do not allow mode changes.

500 Notice that the conditions 1 to 4 can be notably severe. Hence, small changes in the system temperatures can cause chattering problems, contributing to undesirable jumps on operating modes and abrupt inputs changes. In addition, conditions 1 and 2 can be satisfied simultaneously, and one prevalent mode must be prioritized. Thus, a tuning parameter ΔT and a mean variable \bar{T} calculated
505 over a moving time window to minimize the possibilities of process oscillations and better adjust the systems gradient temperature are proposed, keeping the entire plant temperature balanced. Therefore, the stated conditions are mathematically interpreted as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
J_1(t) &= \Delta T_1 - (\bar{T}_{t,2,3}(t) - \bar{T}_{sc,o}(t)) \\
J_2(t) &= \Delta T_2 - (\bar{T}_{sc,o}(t) - \bar{T}_{t,1,1}(t)) \\
J_3(t) &= \Delta T_3 - (T_{g,in}(t) - T_{ref}(t)) \\
J_4(t) &= \Delta T_4 - (T_{ref}(t) - T_g(t)) \\
J_5(t) &= T_s \cdot K_t - counter(t)
\end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

in which T_s is the time sample, K_t is the integer multiplier to define how long
510 the process should operate in a specific plant configuration, T_{ref} is the gas heater output temperature reference and $counter(t)$ is a timer to measure the elapsed time during the plant operation, in which is zeroed when a new mode is activated. Therefore, for each process condition in Eq. (13), an auxiliary

variable is associated by the following statements:

$$[J_1(t) \leq 0] \leftrightarrow [\delta_{T_1} = 1] \quad (14a)$$

$$[J_2(t) \leq 0] \leftrightarrow [\delta_{T_2} = 1] \quad (14b)$$

$$[J_3(t) \leq 0] \leftrightarrow [\delta_{GH_1} = 1] \quad (14c)$$

$$[J_4(t) \leq 0] \leftrightarrow [\delta_{GH_2} = 1] \quad (14d)$$

$$[J_5(t) \leq 0] \leftrightarrow [\delta_{mode} = 1] \quad (14e)$$

$$[\delta_{GH} = \widetilde{\delta_{GH_1}} \wedge \delta_{GH_2}] \quad (14f)$$

515 It is noteworthy that for each mixed logical statement in Eqs. (14a) to (14f), a respective set of linear mixed-integer inequalities is associated, as described in Eqs. (11) and (12).

3.4. Objective function

The control objective presented in this work aims to maintain the inlet tem-
 520 perature of the load system within the defined reference temperature range. For this, a zone control formulation is presented, in which the temperature set-point is a decision variable of the optimization problem, defined between the bound limits constraints. Consequently, the control structure must control the outlet temperature of the gas heater, which is the last system before hot water enters
 525 the heat exchanger. Therefore, based on systems modeling, output predictions and the formulation of mixed integer inequality constraints, the optimization problem of the HPNMPC is given as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\Delta z(t), \delta_p(t), T_{ref}(t)} J_{HPNMPC}, \\ J_{HPNMPC} = \sum_{i=1}^{i=N_p} \left| \hat{T}_g(t+i|t) - T_{ref}(t+i|t) \right|_R^2 - \\ \sum_{m=1}^{m=n_m} \sum_{j=0}^{j=N_c-1} |\Delta \mathbf{z}_m(t+j|t)|_{Q_z}^2 \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

subjected to, $\forall i = 1, \dots, N_p$ and $\forall j = 0, \dots, N_c - 1$

$$\delta_p(t) \quad \forall p = \{m \in [1, \dots, n_m], T_1, T_2, GH_1, GH_2, GH, mode\} \quad (16a)$$

$$u(t) = \Delta u(t|t) + u(t-1) \quad (16b)$$

$$\Delta u_{1_{min}} \leq \Delta u_1(t+j|t) \leq \Delta u_{1_{max}} \quad (16c)$$

$$\Delta u_{2_{min}} \leq \Delta u_2(t+j|t) \leq \Delta u_{2_{max}} \quad (16d)$$

$$\Delta u_{3_{min}} \leq \Delta u_3(t+j|t) \leq \Delta u_{3_{max}} \quad (16e)$$

$$u_{1_{min}} \leq u_1(t+j|t) \leq u_{1_{max}} \quad (16f)$$

$$u_{2_{min}} \leq u_2(t+j|t) \leq u_{1_{max}} \quad (16g)$$

$$u_{3_{min}} \leq u_3(t+j|t) \leq u_{1_{max}} \quad (16h)$$

$$T_{sc,o_{min}} \leq \hat{T}_{sc,o}(t+i|t) \leq T_{sc,o_{max}} \quad (16i)$$

$$T_{ref_{min}} \leq T_{ref}(t+i|t) \leq T_{ref_{max}} \quad (16j)$$

$$\text{Process models, Eqs. (1) to (5)} \quad (16k)$$

$$\text{Predicted outputs, Eq. (9)} \quad (16l)$$

$$\text{MIQP, Eqs. (11) and (12)} \quad (16m)$$

$$\text{Process constraints, Eqs. (14a) to (14f)} \quad (16n)$$

530 wherein \mathbf{Q}_z and R are the weighting factors for the inputs and outputs, respectively. Notice that \mathbf{Q}_z is a square weighting matrix of dimension $[n_u \cdot n_m \times n_u \cdot n_m]$.

The optimization problem formulated in Eqs. (15) and (16) can now be simply solved by an MIQP solver. Moreover, this formulation does not account
 535 for combining the different operating modes to achieve the desired T_{ref} . Instead, the operating conditions are defined as inequality constraints and are satisfied by the MIQP solution. As a result, the HPNMPC controller provides ideal input increments to control the plant in its proper operating mode, whose solution is given by converting the auxiliary variables δ_p into the respective states of all
 540 integer variables described in Table 1.

It is worth noting that the operating modes can also be predicted over the control horizon since the binary variables δ_p are associated with the inputs and are established as decision variables. It means that the proposed HPNMPC can predict the future operating modes, considering the disturbances assumptions and nonlinearities approximations for the outputs prediction model of Eq. (8).
545

3.5. Control approaches overview

The proposed hybrid control strategy aims to take advantage of the controller's prediction feature to enhance control and process performance. Therefore, it is essential to establish a benchmark to evaluate the presented HPNMPC. This work proposes the conventional PNMPC as a control strategy reference, which is the same approach presented for the HPNMPC without the linear mixed-integer inequalities. That is, the PNMPC control optimization problem is defined as follows:
550

$$\begin{aligned} & \min_{\Delta z(t), T_{ref}(t)} J_{PNMPC}, \\ J_{PNMPC} &= \sum_{i=1}^{i=N_p} \left| \hat{T}_g(t+i|t) - T_{ref}(t+i|t) \right|_R^2 - \sum_{j=0}^{j=N_c-1} |\Delta \mathbf{u}(t+j|t)|_{\mathbf{Q}_u}^2 \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

subjected to constraints of Eq. 16b to 16l, $\forall i = 1, \dots, N_p$ and $\forall j = 0, \dots, N_c - 1$

Notice that the linear model used to predict the process outputs is the conventional one, wherein matrix \mathbf{G} is computed only with the model equations of the current operating mode of the plant. Thus, the matrix \mathbf{G} is calculated by the linear approximation on the operating point of the activated nonlinear system models. In addition, the decision variables are the models inputs $\Delta \mathbf{u}$ and the temperature reference T_{ref} , and the weighting matrix \mathbf{Q}_u has the dimensions $[nu \times nu]$.
560

Since the PNMPC control layer does not define the operating mode, an external decision-maker framework must compute the process constraints and define the plant configuration. In order to identify the main control structure differences, Fig. 5 depicts both control strategies formulated in this work.
565

Fig 5. Control scheme of the HPNMPC (A) and PNMPC (B) for the CIESOL facility.

It is worth mentioning that the decision-maker structure holds the same process constraints formulated for the HPNMPC, which provides the same conditions for both strategies. Moreover, both strategies consider the robust filter Fr to address uncertainties and miss-match scenarios.

570 **4. Results and discussion**

To asses the performance of the HPNMPC strategy, study case scenarios are simulated in different process conditions using real collected data from the CIESOL plant. Moreover, the HPNMPC is compared to a classical PNMPC in order to evaluate the process and control performances concerning the computa-
 575 tion of the operating process modes, either internally (HPNMPC) or externally

(PNMPC). By adopting the decision-maker, the classical PNMPC uses the defined operating mode m to calculate the matrices \mathbf{G} and $\mathbf{F}_{m_{k-1}}$ in each sample time. The presented results are obtained using the MathWorks MATLAB 2017b software and the IBM CPLEX Optimizer Studio 12.8.0v solver.

580 The simulated scenarios are: i) Sunny day scenario, in which solar irradiance has cloudless disturbances, and data are collected on April 18, 2021; ii) Cloudy day scenario, where there are strong disturbances in solar irradiance and the data are collected on April 7, 2021; and iii) uncertainty scenario, the same data as the sunny day scenario are used, but with variations in the model parameters. Specifically, it is assumed $\pm 5\%$ of variation in parameters H_{sc} , $U_{t,1,1}$, $U_{t,1,2}$,
585 $H_{t,1,3}$, $H_{t,2,1}$, $H_{t,2,2}$, $H_{t,2,3}$ and H_{ga} .

For the simulation purpose, the controller sample time is defined $T_s = 5$ s. The T_{ref} for the three scenarios are the same, initiating at 67 °C, and later changed to 70 °C and then 75 °C, finally reducing to 70 °C again. In addition,
590 the mean variables \bar{T} is calculated over $24 \cdot T_s$ moving time window, which is equivalent to 2 min. Moreover, to present only the activation/deactivation of the gas heater, the $Reg(t)$ is set to 0.5. The process constraints and the controller tuning parameters are the same for all scenarios, and those are detailed in Table 4. The defined parameters were obtained by means of simulation tests, whereas
595 the input limits were established according to the actual physical limits of each manipulated variable.

Moreover, four indices in order to objectively evaluate the control performances are proposed: the number of mode changes, the elapsed time operating with the gas heater, the Sum of the Absolute Error (SAE), which is calculated
600 when the controlled variables is out of the reference range and the Sum of Con-

Table 4: Control tuning parameters for the simulated Scenarios 1, 2 and 3.

Control Parameters	Values
N_p	12
N_c	5
\mathbf{Q}	[1, 3, 3]
R	100
$[\Delta u_{1_{max}}, \Delta u_{2_{max}}, \Delta u_{3_{max}}]$	[3, 1, 1]
$[\Delta u_{1_{min}}, \Delta u_{2_{min}}, \Delta u_{3_{min}}]$	[-3, -1, -1]
$u_{1_{max}}$	12
$[u_{1_{min}}, u_{2_{min}}, u_{3_{min}}]$	[3, 1, 1]
$T_{sc,o_{max}}$	110
$T_{sc,o_{min}}$	25
SP_{lim}	1
$T_{ref_{max}}$	$T_{ref} + SP_{lim}$
$T_{ref_{min}}$	$T_{ref} - SP_{lim}$
ΔT_1	3
ΔT_2	1.5
ΔT_3	3
ΔT_4	3
K_t	60

trol Increments (SCI), given by:

$$\begin{aligned}
 SAE &= \begin{cases} \sum_{k=1}^{k=t_f} |T_{he,h,in}(k) - T_{ref_{max}}(k)| & \text{if } T_{he,h,in}(k) \geq T_{ref_{max}}(k) \\ \sum_{k=1}^{k=t_f} |T_{he,h,in}(k) - T_{ref_{min}}(k)| & \text{if } T_{he,h,in}(k) \leq T_{ref_{min}}(k) \end{cases} \quad (18) \\
 SCI &= \sum_{k=2}^{k=t_f} \left| \frac{u(k) - u(k-1)}{u(k-1)} \right|
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 6 depicts the heat exchanger input disturbances in the cold side, that is, the loads disturbances in the input temperature $T_{hc,c,in}(t)$ and its respective volumetric flow $u_c(t)$.

Fig 6. Heat Exchanger disturbances - Input temperature of the cold side and volumetric flow for Scenarios 1 and 2.

605 *4.1. Scenario 1 - Sunny day*

In this first scenario, the solar irradiance $I(t)$ corresponds to a clean day, and no substantial variations occur. The solar collector field output temperature starts at 64 °C and the tanks' gradient starts at 63 °C on the lower segment of Tank 1 to 69 °C to the upper segment of Tank 2. The process operation
 610 starts in mode 3, and, therefore, the tanks are in the load mode. Thus, the inlet temperature of the gas heater is 63 °C.

Figure 7 details the controlled variable $T_{he,h,in}(t)$ and the plant modes at each simulation instant. At first, both the HPNMPC and classical PNMPC have similar performance according to the adopted criteria. However, this behavior
 615 changes and the strategies differ for the first 2.5 hours of simulation. Both strategies keep the plant operating without using the gas heater until there is the first increment in the reference, wherein the gas heater is activated. Initially, the gas heater works with the solar collectors and the tanks in load mode, but later only with the solar collectors. As soon as a new reference temperature
 620 increment happens, the tanks return to the load mode. However, when the reference temperature is reduced, both strategies turn the gas heater off. The

Fig 7. Scenario 1 disturbances and outputs - Solar irradiance and ambient temperature disturbances, the inlet temperature of the heat exchanger and the operating modes for the HPN MPC and classical PN MPC

Fig 8. Scenario 1 inputs - manipulated volumetric flows for the HPN MPC and classical PN MPC

heat exchanger inlet temperature is controlled with the plant operating only with the solar collectors. Figure 8 shows the controlled variables. As can be seen, there are small increments in the input variables during the entire simulation,

625 and this happens only when there is a significant increment in the reference.

Table 5: Controller performance indices for Scenario 1 - Sunny day

Control Indices	HPNMPC	PNMPC
SAE [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]	419.17	641.52
$\text{SCI}_{u_1}, \text{SCI}_{u_2}, \text{SCI}_{u_3}$ [-]	[6.71, 10.20, 20.15]	[7.20, 6.57, 24.38]
Mode changes [-]	13	13
Gas heater operating time [min]	150.0	145.0

From this first scenario results, it can be noted that the proposed process conditions can appropriately set the operating mode for the thermal solar plant, either for the HPNMPC or the PNMPC with the decision-maker structure in charge to determine the current plant mode. Furthermore, an appropriate adjustment of the control tuning and the process conditions definitions can help minimize the variations of the controller inputs, which can be very attractive for systems operating with constants disturbances, such as the thermal solar system. Regarding the HPNMPC performance, Table 5 details the performance indices for both strategies, including the SAE and SCI index for the three controlled variables (notice that the objective is to reduce both indices rates). The HPNMPC presents much smaller SAE and SCI indices related to the defined operating modes by the hybrid strategy. As can be noted, the significant differences occur approximately at 10:40 h, when the classical PNMPC does not use the gas heater for two periods and causes the temperature to reduce considerably, increasing the output error, see Fig. 7.

As observed, the mode changes entail variations in the system dynamics, mainly regarding the gas heater's activation, which considerably affects the controlled output. Therefore, determining the minimum time for mode changing adequately, K_t , assuredly contributes to reducing the output error. Moreover, this aspect suggests that the ability of the Hybrid controller to take into account mode changes within the prediction horizon may be decisive for the correct operation of these systems.

4.2. Scenario 2 - Cloudy day

This second scenario proposes to evaluate the HPNMPC controller when
650 significant disturbances occur in the solar irradiance. The initial temperature for
the solar collector field is 60.0 °C, and the tanks begin the simulation with 48.6
°C for the lower segment of Tank 1 and 51.8 °C for the upper segment of Tank
2. The plant operation already initiates in mode 6, which sets the activation of
the gas heater and the tanks operating in the load mode. Therefore, the inlet
655 temperature of the gas heater is 48.6 °C, which is distant from the reference
temperature, being necessary to activate the gas heater as stated in the process
conditions constraints.

Figures 9 and 10 depicted the controlled variable and the modes and the
manipulated volumetric flows for both the PNMPC and HPNMPC. From these
660 figures, it can be seen that both control strategies perform identically until
approximately 12.5 h, keeping the gas heater activated to achieve the desired
temperature for the heat exchanger system. In this stage, the accumulation tank
temperatures are distant from the reference. Thus, the plant configuration is set
to increase the tanks' temperature and keep the system's temperature gradient
665 uniform, following the process requirements. The process initial conditions and
the low variations of the meteorological circumstances make both controllers
act equally at the first half of the experiment. Then, when the system gains
substantial energy and there are significant variations on the solar irradiance,
the behavior of the control strategies is different. The gas heater is turned off,
670 and both strategies alternate among modes 1, 2, and 3. It is notable that, even
with substantial variations in the solar irradiance, the controlled variables do
not oscillate, and, once again, a well-designed process condition is capable of
dealing with the process disturbances.

Fig 9. Scenario 2 disturbances and outputs - Solar irradiance and ambient temperature disturbances, the inlet temperature of the heat exchanger and the operating modes for the HPNMPC and classical PNMPC

Fig 10. Scenario 2 inputs - manipulated volumetric flows for the HPNMPC and classical PNMPC

Table 6 presents the control and process performance indices for Scenario 2. It can be noted that both strategies can control the output with no significant differences, keeping minor differences on every index. A slight advantage appears

for the HPNMPC regarding the SAE, which can be justified when the Hybrid strategy operates a larger time in mode 3 while the classical PNMPC operated in mode 1.

Table 6: Controller performance indices for Scenario 2 - Cloudy day

Control Indices	HPNMPC	PNMPC
SAE [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]	227.95	248.44
$\text{SCI}_{u_1}, \text{SCI}_{u_2}, \text{SCI}_{u_3}$ [\cdot]	[8.59, 10.36, 19.32]	[7.68, 9.26, 14.43]
Mode changes [\cdot]	17	15
Gas heater operating time [min]	204	204

680 *4.3. Scenario 3 - Sunny day with uncertainties*

Lastly, Scenario 3 simulates the same process conditions as Scenario 1 but with internal controller model uncertainties. As presented in the work of Plucenio et al. [25], the PNMPC formulation considers the integral of the filtered error in the model prediction in order to embed robustness to the algorithm. For Scenarios 1 and 2, since there were no differences between the internal controller model and the simulated plant, the filter output is always zero. However, for Scenario 3, a miss-match case happens, and the model differences will generate an output predicted error. This simulated scenario intends to evaluate the control and process performance applying the filtered predicted error for the proposed HPNMPC in order to demonstrate that the hybrid controller is, in addition, robust and capable of dealing with model uncertainties. The notation HPNMPC is presented as the nominal case, which is precisely like the Scenario 1 output, and HPNMPC_{un} as the uncertainty model case.

Figure 11 illustrates the controller outputs for both the HPNMPC nominal case and the HPNMPC_{un} . A slight variation in the control outputs can change the plant configuration and leads to different operating plant modes. After the second increment in the temperature reference, the HPNMPC_{un} reaches an operating condition that turns off the gas heater, which causes the heat exchanger inlet temperature to decrease considerably until δ_{mode} is activated

Fig 11. Scenario 3 disturbances and outputs - Solar irradiance and ambient temperature disturbances, the inlet temperature of the heat exchanger and the operating modes for the HPNMPC and HPNMPC with uncertainties

Fig 12. Scenario 1 inputs - manipulated volumetric flows for the HPNMPC and HPNMPC with uncertainties

700 again, which allows the controller to go to another mode. This behavior is due to the model uncertainties. The simulated plant does not behave as predicted by the internal model of the controller, leading to diverse plant conditions and

variations in operating modes compared to the nominal HPNMPC.

Table 7 depicts the performance indices for both the HPNMPC and the
705 HPNMPC with uncertainties. It can be seen that the HPNMPC with uncer-
tainties, even though it includes the filtered error, does not keep the nominal
operation and its performance deteriorates in comparison to the nominal case.
Since the miss-match scenario Nevertheless, this strategy is quite robust and
could keep the system operation stable and, in addition, attend to the process
710 requirements, even though the imposed uncertainties are notably strong since
the output errors are propagated due to the system model connections. Further-
more, in this work, the same tuning was proposed for both the miss-match case
and the nominal case exclusively to demonstrate the robustness of the hybrid
algorithm. However, the hybrid strategy performance can be improved as the
715 controller parameters are adjusted.

Table 7: Controller performance indices for Scenario 3 - Uncertainties case in sunny day

Control Indices	HPNMPC	HPNMPC
	nominal	with uncertainties
SAE [°C]	419.17	529.70
$SCI_{u_1}, SCI_{u_2}, SCI_{u_3}$ [·]	[6.71, 10.20, 20.15]	[8.17, 16.73, 38.92]
Mode changes [·]	13	16
Gas Heater operating time [min]	150.0	168

4.4. Computational processing effort

Lastly, in order to evaluate the HPNMPC computational control perfor-
mance, Table 8 demonstrated the mean elapsed time for different control hori-
zons. These results intend to compare the proposed control algorithm, which is
720 formulated to attend to the process conditions, to control approaches that use
the process configuration as a combinatorial solution to achieve the control ob-
jective, as presented by Álvarez et al. [24]. The results are performed only in a
part-time simulation of 1000 samples time to demonstrate the mean elapsed time

for calculating the controllers' solutions. As can be seen, as the control horizon
725 N_c increases, the processing time also increases, but in a linear way, differently
from the exponential increase for combinatorial approaches. Moreover, the HP-
NMPC presents a higher computational cost than the PNMPC approach, which
is expected since the hybrid strategy includes more linear inequalities computed
by the optimization solver.

Table 8: Computational effort calculated by the mean elapsed time of the controller calculation
at each sample time

Control Horizon N_c	Computational cost (mean time) [s]		
	HPNMPC	PNMPC	Álvarez et. al. (2016) [24]
1	0.399	0.218	0.114
2	0.434	0.221	0.684
3	0.457	0.234	4.104
4	0.495	0.232	24.624
5	0.505	0.233	147.744
10	0.667	0.268	-

730 4.5. Discussion

This work introduces a practical nonlinear predictive controller that accounts
for process operation requirements to control a thermal solar plant in its dif-
ferent system configurations. The proposed HPNMPC, an extension of the
classical PNMPC, combines a straightforward and robust control formulation
735 that includes the computation of future outputs using nonlinear models and
incorporates process conditions and the plant operating modes in a single con-
trol layer. As a result, the controller provides the correct plant operating mode
and the optimal inputs for the specific systems configurations. The approach is
presented to control a thermal plant facility using a heat exchanger as a system
740 demand unit. The results are provided in a simulation scenario, using validated
hybrid models of the CIESOL facility.

In order to present the benefits of the proposed strategy, the HPNMPC is compared to the classical PNMPC with an external decision-maker structure in two scenarios, with low and substantial levels of disturbances. The results depicted in Figures 7 to 10 demonstrate that the HPNMPC can eliminate the decision-maker from its function and provide the proper operating modes for the system configuration. Furthermore, since the HPNMPC includes the calculation of the plant modes along the prediction horizon, this approach is in advance compared to a controller with an external framework. This slight difference can change the entire plant operation throughout the day since the system combinations can significantly alter the temperature profiles. Nevertheless, comparing both strategy performances in Tables 5 and 6, the HPNMPC has a better control performance regarding the SAE index, while for the other measured indices, the performances are very similar.

It is worth mention that an appropriate representation of the process conditions is crucial for a solid operational performance. As suggested in Section 3.3, the proposed maneuvers of implementing main variables instead of a single variable value, using parameters ΔT and imposing a minimum time condition to switch modes, contribute to minimizing the chattering effects, unexpected mode jumps and smooth out the inequality constraints of the process. Furthermore, the well-tuned process conditions keep the entire system profile regular, minimizing abrupt variations of the system's volumetric flows, as demonstrated in Figures 8, 10 and 12.

Regarding computational performance, the HPNMPC presents an exciting approach to minimize computational costs. Since it converts logical statements into mixed-logical inequalities, the controller can use MIQP solvers that are already well established and provide a short processing time. Moreover, since the presented approach uses the plant modes as process constraints and not as the controller degrees of freedom, the HPNMPC does not perform combination calculations of the possible operating modes over the prediction horizon. In contrast, the optimal input solutions are properly calculated respecting the plant configuration. Furthermore, for the sake of comparison, as presented in

Table 8, the computational costs of combinatorial solutions increase exponentially concerning the number of plant modes and the control horizon. In the
775 herein presented approach, the computational costs increase linearly and are significantly lower than the strategy proposed by [24]. On the other hand, the HPNMPC presents a higher computational cost due to the necessity of calculating the output prediction matrices \mathbf{G}_M and $\hat{\mathbf{F}}_{m_{k-1}}$ for all the operating modes. In contrast, the classical PNMPC calculates for only one mode.

780 Finally, the developed control strategy can also be implemented in model uncertainties scenarios. The HPNMPC allows using a robust filter that corrects the predicted outputs in the miss-match cases. The results presented in Figures 11 and 12 and Table 7 demonstrate that it is possible to keep the plant operating in an appropriate outline when significant differences in the model parameters
785 occur. Notice that the proposed uncertainty scenario contributes to propagate and increase the output error since the parameters are changed over the three thermal plant subsystems. In other words, the error in the solar collector field model is expanded by the error in the accumulation tanks and also by the gas heater models. Moreover, since the models present persistent disturbances, the
790 predicted output error is never zero. Nevertheless, the HPNMPC with a robust filter keeps the operation stable and presents a satisfactory performance. Indeed, a proper recalibration of the controller tuning parameters is required to improve its performance in modeling uncertainty cases.

5. Conclusions

795 This work presents a hybrid nonlinear model predictive control strategy for controlling a thermal solar plant facility that supplies energy to HVAC systems of a building. The proposed control framework is given as HPNMPC, in which MLD models and process operation conditions are formulated in a single-layer optimization problem. Consequently, the resulting nonlinear optimization problem
800 is simplified to a MIQP, being efficiently solved by traditional optimization solvers. The HPNMPC provides both the optimal volumetric flows and the

single operating mode following the established process conditions.

To assess the efficiency of the proposed control framework, the HPNMPC is compared to a classical PNMPC associated with an additional control structure to define the particular operating mode. Specifically, both strategies are examined into three distinct scenarios, simulating real process conditions and uncertainties applied to validated plant models. In concerning the simulation results topic, it should be noted that the HPNMPC presents satisfactory performance and the performance index of the controller is even better than the simplest PNMPC. For instance, in Scenario 1, the HPNMPC showed an SAE index of up to 35% lower than the conventional PNMPC and a total SCI control effort of 37.06 against 38.15 of the PNMPC plus the decision-maker. Also, the process conditions tuning led the plant to operate in a uniform temperature gradient among all systems, mainly concerning the accumulation tanks and the solar collector field regarding the reference temperature of the heat exchanger. This aspect can undoubtedly reduce the use of the gas heater during nighttime operation and enlarge the plant's operating time. Moreover, on account of the high-fidelity simulation experiments performed, which included variations in the load demand system, the HPNMPC presents exciting perspectives for practical implementation.

One of the main advantages of the proposed strategy is that the HPNMPC can account for the operating modes forecasting over the control horizon. This premise offers intriguing prospects since the controller can provide optimal inputs considering the future mode changes. Furthermore, the proposed HPNMPC with embedded process conditions restrictions presents low computational costs compared to controllers with unrestricted combinatorial operating modes solutions, reaching up almost 300 times less computational processing time.

Particular features must be extended to enhance this work results. Disturbance estimations can help to improve the output prediction, mainly considering the solar irradiance and ambient temperature. Moreover, optimization layers can be combined with the proposed HPNMPC to provide optimal process conditions to improve the entire system efficiency. Future works intend to apply

these frameworks in practical cases.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

⁸³⁵ **Igor M. L. Pataro:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - original draft, review and editing, Visualization. **Juan D. Gil:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - original draft, review and editing, Visualization **Marcus V. Americano da Costa:** Conceptualization,
⁸⁴⁰ Methodology, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - review, Visualization. **José L. Guzmán:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - review, Visualization. **Manuel Berenguel:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - review, Visualization.

⁸⁴⁵ **Declaration of competing interest**

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

⁸⁵⁰ The Authors acknowledge the financial support of National Council for Scientific and Technological Development (CNPq, Brazil) under grant 201143/2019–4. This work has been carried out as part of the project entitled “Microrredes para el autoabastecimiento solar de entornos productivos aislados (Microprod-Solar)” funded by the International Joint Programming initiative of the State
⁸⁵⁵ Research Agency of the Spanish Government, grant PCI2019-103378 and by the Iberoamerican Program for Science and Technology for the Development (CYTED).

Appendix A

Table 9: Model parameters description.* Parameters adjusted using optimization algorithm identification based on the Mean Squared Error (MSE). The variables bound were adequately chosen to correspond to parameters physical properties.

Parameter	Description	Unit
A_g^*	Gas heater water conduct's external surface	0.11 [m ²]
A_{he}^*	Heat exchanger area	0.529 [m ²]
A_{sc}	Solar collector pipe cross-section area	1.13·10 ⁻⁴ [m ²]
$A_{t,1,1}, A_{t,1,2}, A_{t,1,3}^*$	Tank 1 internal contact area between segments	1.9, 2.2, 1.9 [m ²]
$A_{t,2,1}, A_{t,2,2}, A_{t,2,3}^*$	Tank 2 internal contact area between segments	1.6, 1.8, 1.6 [m ²]
c_s	Conversion factor to account for connections, number of modules and m ³ /s conversion	10·3600 [s/h]
C_f	Specific heat capacity of water	4018 [J/(Kg·°C)]
C_{fc}	Specific heat capacity of water at the heat exchanger cold side	4018 [J/(Kg·°C)]
H_{sc}^*	Solar collector field global losses coefficient	79.17 [J/(s·°C)]
L	Collector absorber tube length	5.825 [m]
n_{sc}	Number of series-connections in a collectors group	8
$SA_{t,a,1}, SA_{t,a,2}, SA_{t,a,3}^*$	Tanks ith-tank jth-segment surface area	4.8842, 2, 4.8842 [m ²]
$T_{g,gas}^*$	Combustion gases temperature	349.9 [°C]
U_{ga}^*	Gas heater thermal losses coefficient	1.52 [W/(m ² ·°C)]
U_{gto}^*	Gas heater heat transfer coefficient	157.87 [W/°C]
$U_{t,1,1}, U_{t,1,2}, U_{t,1,3}^*$	Tanks losses coefficient per surface unit	5.0, 5.0, 3.5 [W/(m ² ·°C)]
$U_{t,2,1}, U_{t,2,2}, U_{t,2,3}^*$	Tanks losses coefficient per surface unit	0.5, 0.5, 0.5 [W/(m ² ·°C)]
$U_{t,a,s/1,s/2}^*$	Tank global heat transfer coefficient per surface unit between the consecutive segments	1.0·10 ⁴ [W/(m ² ·°C)]
V_g^*	Gas heater fluid volume	0.0998 [m ³]
$V_{t,a,1}, V_{t,a,2}, V_{t,a,3}^*$	Tank jth-segment volume	1.8, 1.4, 1.8 [m ³]
α_{he}^*	Heat exchanger heat transfer coefficient	3.65·10 ³ [W/(m ² ·°C)]
β^*	Irradiance model parameter	0.432 [m]
ρ_f	Water density	1000 [Kg/m ³]
η_{he}	Heat exchanger auxiliary factor	[...]
θ_{he}	Heat exchanger auxiliary factor 2	[...]
τ^*	Heat exchanger time constant	0.1 [s]

Appendix B

Table 10: Models variables description

Variables	Description
GH	Gas heater activation
I	Global Irradiance [W/m^2]
Reg	Gas heater regulation
SCS	Solar collector field activation
TOS	Accumulation tank activation
$T_{ss_{he,c,o}}$	Heat exchanger cold side outlet temperature in steady state [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
$T_{ss_{he,h,o}}$	Heat exchanger hot side outlet temperature in steady state [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
T_a	Ambient temperature [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
T_g	Output temperature of the gas heater [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
$T_{g,in}$	Gas heater inlet temperature [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
$T_{he,c,in}$	Heat exchanger cold side inlet temperature [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
$T_{he,c,o}$	Heat exchanger cold side outlet temperature [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
$T_{he,h,in}$	Heat exchanger hot side inlet temperature [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
$T_{he,h,o}$	Heat exchanger hot side outlet temperature [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
$T_{sc,in}$	Inlet temperature of the solar collector field [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
$T_{sc,o}$	Output temperature of the solar collector field [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
\bar{T}_{sc}	Equivalent absorber tube mean temperature [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
$T_{t,a,s}$	Temperature of ath tank and sth tank segment [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
$T_{t,in}$	Inlet temperature of the accumulation tanks [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
u_{eq}	Equivalent collector volumetric flow [m^3/s]
u_1	Pump volumetric flow [m^3/s]
u_2	Solar collector field volumetric flow [m^3/h]
u_3	Gas heater and heat exchanger volumetric flow [m^3/s]
u_c	Gas heater cold side volumetric flow [m^3/s]

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